

A smart-sensing AI-driven platform for scalable, low-cost hydroponic units

D2.5 Procurement of 2 additional Multi-modal Sensor Kits

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RESPONSIBLE AUTHOR	Niklas Galler (nr21 DESIGN)

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ACRONYMS LIST

CHSK	Crop-Health Sensor Kit
CSU	Communications and Storage Unit
DIY	Do it yourself
MMSK	Multi-modal Sensor Kit
NCK	Nutrient-Content Kit

TABLE OF CONTENTS

LIST OF FIGURES.....	6
1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	7
2 PROCUREMENT OF 2 MULTI-MODAL SENSOR KITS.....	8
3 MANUAL OF GOHYDRO SENSOR KITS.....	12
4 CONCLUSIONS.....	63

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure Number	Figure Caption
Figure 1	Schematic Representation of the GOhydro platform concept. The MMSK, which is essentially the front-end of the platform is shown on the left-hand side with respect to the hydroponic installation in the dashed blue frame. The “back-end” consisting of the AI data-driven platform and the e-agronomist mobile app are shown in the yellow dashed frame.
Figure 2	Photographs taken during the procurement of the 2 additional MMSK. In the first 3 picture, Dr Pythagoras Karampimperis (CEO of SCiO and project co-ordinator)) is demonstrating how the kits are assembled, while in the last picture Dr Reed Cowden (key researcher from UCHP) is assembling his own MMSK.
Figure 3	Photographs of the hydroponic installation at USAMV where the MMSK can be seen as part of the installation
Figure 4	Photographs of the hydroponic installation at USAMV where the MMSK can be seen as part of the installation. Professor Teodor Rusu is inspecting the crops, while the MMSK is continuously monitoring the environmental conditions
Figure 5	Photographs of the hydroponic installation at UCHP during the preparation phase. The MMSK is at the point of being assessed in terms of the optimum point to be installed.

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

One of the main technical objectives of the GOHYDRO project is the development of a Multi-modal Sensor Kit (MMSK) capable of monitoring at pre-determined intervals the environmental factors affecting the hydroponic cultures of microgreens, the quality of the water feeding the plants as well as the nutrient content of the microgreens. This kit has as a main task to collect information about the cultivation conditions and the quality of the microgreens and communicate the relevant information to the mobile application of the e-agronomist that will notify the user about the health of the crops and provide suggestions about necessary condition arrangements. The MMSK was developed through a dedicated work package (WP2), which had received input from WP1 “Nutrient and environmental needs for microgreens” with regards to the specific parameters that must be monitored for a successful hydroponic installation. The entire design process, specifications, requirements, fabrication and component integration were all covered through the completed deliverables D2.1-D2.4 and through Tasks 2.1-2.4.

Deliverable D2.5 is the culmination of WP2 and provides two MMSKs to be used by partners USAMV and UCPH in their hydroponic installations. Even though typically D2.5 is DEMONSTRATOR, this report is an accompanying explanatory document that showcases the production of the additional MMSKs (comprised of the CHSK and CSU), their delivery to the two partners in Denmark (partner UCPH) and Romania (USAMV) that took place during the annual technical meeting of the consortium, and their successful installation in the respective units of the partners. As a reminder, the photonics-based NCK is installed and will be tested only in the hydroponic installation in Greece (SCiO). *As a matter of fact the deliverable exceeded the expectations*, since instead of two, three MMSKs were actually fabricated and procured to the partners, one in Denmark and two in Romania. The installed MMSKs will generate the data of D4.2 “Evaluation results from experiments in semi-controlled realistic installations” and D4.3 “Report on validation of microgreens production in operational settings”.

2 PROCUREMENT OF 2 MULTI-MODAL SENSOR KITS

As already analyzed in great detail in all other deliverables of WP2, GOhydro as a whole aims at developing a cost-efficient smart-sensing ICT platform capable of monitoring the crops' health and nutrient content of hydroponically cultivated microgreens in order to optimize the cultivation process and allow the harvest of the best possible products in an urban setting. The front-end of the platform consists of the MMSK, which is responsible for the real-time monitoring, collection and transmission of the environmental parameters and the water quality of the hydroponic installation. The transmitted data are fed to the AI-driven component and from there through to the mobile application. The application serves as an e- agronomist providing tips and suggestions on the health of the crops and the parameters that need to change in order to optimize the hydroponic culturing of microgreens. The GOhydro platform concept is depicted in Figure 1. The MMSK is divided into 3 major components (all analyzed and described in D2.1-2.4): **(1) the Crop Health Sensor Kit (CHSK)** responsible for monitoring the temperature, humidity, light intensity at the installation as well as the electroconductivity and pH of the water in the tank (indicating the quality of the watering), **(2) a photonics-based kit** that will determine the nutrient content of the microgreens through their pulps (**Nutrient-content Kit, NCK**), and **(3) the communications and storage unit (CSU)** that stores and transmits the data collected by the kits to the GOhydro data-driven platform.

Figure 1 Schematic Representation of the GOhydro platform concept. The MMSK, which is essentially the front-end of the platform is shown on the left-hand side with respect to the hydroponic installation in the dashed blue frame. The “back-end” consisting of the AI data-driven platform and the e-agronomist mobile app are shown in the yellow dashed frame.

The 3 additional MMSK that were prepared in-house at SCiO were based on the designs of D2.1-D2.4 as developed by nr21 with the aid of the various design sprints and following the specifications and requirements set in D2.1. The kits were comprised of the off-the-shelf components and the casings that were prepared by a 3d-printer (following the designs of nr21, D2.3) The 3 MMSKs are comprised only of the CHSK and CSU units, since the high-risk NCK will be tested only at the hydroponic installation in Greece by NCSR-D, but will also receive samples produced by UCHP’s hydroponic installation. The 2 MMSKs were handed to the partners from UCHP and USAMV during the annual technical meeting of the consortium that took place in Athens (July 13-14, 2022), while the additional third MMSK was shipped to Romania one month later. The partners were shown how to assemble the kits on the spot during the technical meeting, while a manual was provided (see next

chapter). Some photographs from the actual exchange and training can be seen in Figure 2. The MMSKs are already installed at the hydroponic cultures of UCHP and USAMV (Figure 3) and data are received at SciO by the CSUs.

Figure 2 Photographs taken during the procurement of the 2 additional MMSK. In the first 3 picture, Dr Pythagoras Karampimperis (CEO of SciO and project co-ordinator) is demonstrating how the kits are assembled, while in the last picture Dr Reed Cowden (key researcher from UCHP) is assembling his own MMSK.

Figure 3 Photographs of the hydroponic installation at USAMV where the MMSK can be seen as part of the installation. Professor Teodor Rusu is inspecting the crops, while the MMSK is continuously monitoring the environmental conditions.

Figure 4 Photographs of the hydroponic installation at UCHP during the preparation phase. The MMSK is at the point of being assessed in terms of the optimum point to be installed.

3 MANUAL OF GOHYDRO SENSOR KITS

The MMSKs were developed around the DIY concept, therefore apart from the choice of components and the instructions on how to build the casings with a 3D printer, a manual of instructions was additionally developed by nr21 DESIGN. Again, following the concept of DIY, the manual was developed in an illustrative and easy-to-follow way. The manual can be available to anyone who wishes to fabricate the GOhydro sensor kits.

GO HYDRO SENSOR KIT

REQUIRED COMPONENTS

SENSOR KIT HOUSING

SENSOR KIT INLAYS

CSU HOUSING

EXTERNAL SENSORS HOUSING

ELECTRICAL COMPONENTS

MECHANICAL COMPONENTS

SENSOR PROBES AND BATTERY

TRANSPARENT SHEET

DOWNLOAD PRINTING FILES

BUY SOURCING PARTS

ELECTRICAL COMPONENTS OVERVIEW

Pi4
RASPERRY
PI 4 MODEL B

TDS
TDS-METER
BOARD

Pi0
RASPERRY
PI ZERO

HUM
HUMIDITY
SENSOR

PiH
RASPERRY
HAT PCB

UV
UV SENSOR

pH
PH-METER BOARD

PWR
POWER BUTTON

EXTERNAL COMPONENTS OVERVIEW

pH

PH-METER

PB

POWERBANK

TDS

TDS-METER

TMP

TEMPERATURE SENSOR

MECHANICAL COMPONENTS OVERVIEW

TRANSPARENT SHEET

RASPBERRY PI
HEATSINK

O-RING X2
(ID 2MM OD 96MM)

PCB SPACER X4

M4 NUTS

GLANDS X3
PG7

M4 * 15 X6

FAN 25MM FOR
RASPBERRY PI

M2 * 10 X4

M2 * 6 X10

PRINTS OVERVIEW

Sensor kit housing

Sensor kit inlays

CSU housing

External sensors housing

PRINTING ORIENTATION

PRINTING ORIENTATION

PRINTING ORIENTATION

TRANSPARENT SHEET CUTTING GUIDE

SCALE 1:1

1A SENSOR KIT CAPS

0

1A SENSOR KIT CAPS

01

0

1A SENSOR KIT CAPS

01

1A SENSOR KIT CAPS

1B SENSOR KIT HOUSING

1B SENSOR KIT HOUSING

01

1B SENSOR KIT HOUSING

02

1B SENSOR KIT HOUSING

03

1B SENSOR KIT HOUSING

2A EXTERNAL SENSORS

UV HUM

2A EXTERNAL SENSORS

01

2A EXTERNAL SENSORS

02

2A EXTERNAL SENSORS

03

2A EXTERNAL SENSORS

04

2A EXTERNAL SENSORS

05

2A EXTERNAL SENSORS

2B INNER COMPONENTS

- Pi0
- PiH
- TDS
- pH

2B INNER COMPONENTS

01

2B INNER COMPONENTS

02

M2 * 6 X10

M2 * 10 X4

TDS

pH

Pi0

PiH

2B INNER COMPONENTS

3A CONNECTION

- pH
- TDS
- TMP
- G

3A CONNECTION

01

G

3A CONNECTION

02

3A CONNECTION

03

3B ASSEMBLY

PWR

3B ASSEMBLY

01

3B ASSEMBLY

02

M4 * 10 X6

3B ASSEMBLY

4A ASSEMBLY

pH

PB

4A ASSEMBLY

01

4A ASSEMBLY

02

4A ASSEMBLY

03

M4 * 15 X6

4A ASSEMBLY

5A CSU BASE

Pi4 F H

5A CSU BASE

01

H

4X M2 * 6 X10

5A CSU BASE

02

F

M2 * 6 X10

5A CSU BASE

03

5A CSU BASE

ASSEMBLY COMPLETE

4 CONCLUSIONS

D2.5 was not only completed successfully without any deviations, but it exceeded the set targets by delivering additional MMSK to the partners. Two MMSKs were completed and procured to the partners at USAMV and UCPH and were successfully installed at their respective hydroponic installations.